

Demand analysis for the BICIPUMA bike-sharing system in UNAM-MEXICO

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Abstract— This paper describes a Pareto Law analysis and ABC classification to determine the most popular service stations in the BICIPUMA bike-sharing system at UNAM-MEXICO.

This analysis will support the administrative and operative management of the system to know the service stations with the greatest affluence in the system; it can be used for a detailed analysis of the demand and its forecast, to subsequently carry out an adequate inventory policy. Knowing this forecast is essential for an efficient bicycle replenishment strategy, thus avoiding surplus or missing units in individual service stations. Likewise, an appropriate management of the inventory in the most used stations will reduce bicycle damage and theft, among other adverse situations.

Keywords—replenishment; Pareto law; urban mobility; ABC classification

I. INTRODUCTION

The growing concern for environmental issues throughout the world has had a direct impact on the forms of transportation used by megacities' inhabitants, causing an increase in the demand for sustainable transport alternatives, among which there is the case of bike sharing (the shared use of a fleet of bicycles). Bike sharing is one of the booming transportation alternatives around the world; its basic principle is simple: individuals use bicycles on an as-needed basis without the costs and responsibilities of bicycle ownership [1].

II. HISTORY OF BIKE SHARING

Initially, European countries with a traditional cycling culture (for example Holland, Germany, Belgium and Denmark) adopted bike sharing systems (BSS), delimiting them to small-scale and non-profit implementations, mainly for social and environmental reasons [2].

The expansion of bike sharing systems was potentiated by the growing concern for the environment and people's welfare and its evolution is closely related to the accelerated development of technology, distinguishing three generations of bike sharing systems. In the first generation, the main component of the system was the bicycle. In the second one, a boot technology is incorporated in which the bicycles are loaned unlocking the security in the parking boot when depositing coins that are reimbursed with the return of the bicycle. The third generation incorporates information

technology that allows the bicycle program management to track bicycles as well as user and system usage information.

At present, there are more than 1,600 cities and/or bike sharing programs operating around the world, with approximately 18,170,000 self-service public use bicycles and pedelecs and 391 programs in planning or under construction [3]. The leader in the bike sharing activity is Europe; in America, bike sharing programs are operated in Canada, Mexico, the United States, Brazil and Chile. Finally, Asia represents the fastest growing bike sharing market, with programs operating in China, South Korea, and Taiwan [2]. Figure 1 shows a map of the bike sharing systems around the world.

Fig. 1. Bikesharing systems in the world; from [3].

III. BIKESHARING IN MEXICO

Mexico City has shown great demographic growth in recent decades, and the consequent exponential growth of motorized transport and the lack of urban planning have led to a drastic increase in air pollution rates and mobility problems. Therefore, the city administration has looked for a sustainable way to help reduce both problems.

The analysis of existing mobility data showed that approximately 50% of the trips correspond to distances of less than 8 km, making the implementation of a bike sharing program viable. As a result, the ECOBICI program was created as a public bicycle system; being a subprogram of the Integral Transportation and Roads Program 2007-2012, it was inaugurated in 2010 with 85 service stations in 6 colonies in Mexico City [4]. In the following years, the program expanded to the historic city centre and surrounding neighbourhoods. The

program was promoted as a mobility tool, which allows the user to move more quickly from one public transport mode to another, or allows them to get closer to their final or intermediate destinations. The system seeks to strengthen public transport, improve the level of road mobility in the city, improve transfer times and to achieve a healthier lifestyle among citizens [5].

IV. BIKESHARING IN THE UNAM

Considering that researchers, academic personnel and students are generally more environmentally aware, as well as the diverse destinations and the large volumes of people that require moving in a large university, the interest that alternative transportation modes have had on school campuses is easily understood. As a pioneer in Mexico, the BICIPUMA system was created in March 2005 in the central campus of the Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México (UNAM) to cover part of its transportation needs, being a free public bike sharing system for those belonging to the university community. One of its main objectives is to promote changes in the community's behaviour patterns, aimed at improving health and increasing the levels of physical activity and well-being. At the same time, the system helps to reduce, in Ciudad Universitaria and its surroundings, vehicular traffic congestion and its harmful effects [6].

The system provides additional means for staff and university students to transfer to different educational centres and institutes from the main accesses to the campus. It can also be used recreationally in free moments to visit interesting sites of the university campus. It consists of 5,980 meters of cycle paths, 14 service stations or modules and 1440 bicycles that serve an average of 4500 daily users. Figure 2 represents the routes and service stations of the BICIPUMA system.

Fig. 2. BICIPUMA routes and modules.

The BICIPUMA loan system is composed of a barcode reader, an operator and a central database in which the bicycles loans, bicycle ID, trip origin station and user ID are stored; the destination of the trip is unknown until the bicycle enters another service station.

Damaged bicycles are collected every fifteen days for review and maintenance; the replenishment of the units is done with a pick-up truck that simply moves them from one service

station to another when the operator reports a lack of inventory. During this transfer, the number and individual ID of the transported bicycles are unknown, making the control, handling and distribution of bicycles inefficient. In addition, when requesting a bicycle, the destination and location of the borrowed bicycle is unknown, causing a loss of control of the unit during the time interval of the loan. This has as a consequence the possible loss of the bicycle and a deficient replenishment strategy, generating at the same time a high degree of inefficiency and high operating costs.

The before mentioned problems are of concern because if the system does not register its demand and, in addition, has an inefficient inventory management, its users may not have a correct disposition of the bicycles, and possibly look for less sustainable and slower means of transport.

V. PARETO LAW AND ABC CLASSIFICATION

The Pareto analysis according to the 80/20 principle is very useful to quickly identify, in a single revision, the set of most important elements or more urgent problems to solve, so as not to waste resources on unnecessary activities. The 80/20 Principle states that there is an inbuilt imbalance between causes and results, inputs and outputs, and effort and reward [7]. Typically, causes, inputs or effort can be divided into two categories:

- the majority, that have little impact
- a small minority, that have a major, dominant impact.

If a problem has several identified causes, generally, 20% of them solve 80% of the problem, while the remaining 80% have a small impact [8].

The development of the Pareto law consists of several steps [9]:

- Step 1:** Develop a list of items that must be analysed,
- Step 2:** Fix possible aspects to be considered in the analysis,
- Step 3:** Order from highest to lowest occurrence and determine the relative and cumulative distribution,
- Step 4:** Analyse the diagram identifying those items that appear most frequently or in a greater amount than other.

The ABC classification system is used to classify products according to their importance, to establish a certain level of existence control and thus have information that can be used to reduce control times, efforts and costs in inventory management [10]. The articles or products can be classified into three classes, according to their importance and value:

- **Type A:** this class includes items that, due to their high cost, high investment in inventory, level of use or contribution to profits, require 100% control of their stocks.
- **Type B:** this set of products comprises the ones that, due to their lower cost and importance, require a lower degree of control.

- **Type C:** this class contains low cost products, or items with low investment levels and little importance for the production process; they only require little supervision on the level of their stocks.

Implementation the ABC classification allows to establish administration priorities and differentiate between the control systems requirements of the items in each category [11]. Among the criteria most commonly used to perform this classification are:

- Classification by unit price
- Classification by total value
- Classification by use and value
- Classification for its contribution to profits

VI. LITERATURE REVIEW

Human mobility patterns have received a certain amount of attention in recent studies. Most of them analyse the trajectories of individuals, but often (as in the case of the data in this study) only aggregated spatio-temporal data are available (e.g. the number of people who at time X is in place Y). Predicting the activity of a bike-sharing system is a problem related to traffic congestion control, which has been traditionally analysed for vehicular traffic. Massive data on the use of shared bicycle services allow to infer the mobility patterns of a large population since in most of the cases bike sharing systems are used as an intermodal transport option, linking them to other transportation forms such as buses, subway etc. Also, the spatio-temporal distribution of the people's movements is analysed, noting that there are clear patterns of user behaviour by service station, season and weekday.

Being able to predict the number of bicycles at service stations can easily lead to an improvement in information on system availability. It can also help improve the service itself, avoiding future empty or crowded stations, when implementing an improved manual redistribution of bicycles by trucks. Both aspects can help increase user satisfaction with the system and make people more likely to use the system, obtaining significant benefits in terms of sustainability [12].

Benchimol [13] described the problem of repositioning bicycles (BRP) and presented a method to deal with station balancing when there are no bicycles in motion. Subsequently, Raviv and Kolka [14] established that a crucial factor for the success of a BSS is its ability to cope reliably with a fluctuating demand. In fact, the main complaints voiced by BSS users are related to the unavailability of bicycles at their point of origin and the lack of lockers at their destinations.

Meeting the demand for bicycles and vacant lockers is a particularly challenging problem due to inherent imbalances in the renting and return rates at different stations. While the passenger flow is roughly balanced over the course of a day, this is not the case with the bicycles flow. The decision on the optimal number of bicycles in the system is a crucial tactical

decision that must be reviewed by the operator whenever demand patterns or station capacity change [14].

Berry et al. [15] build a structural demand model that allows estimating the impact of unknown walking distances to the stations and bike-availability on ridership, using public transportation data in different BCC stations and at different times.

Kabra et al. [16] proposed an origin-density model composed by a model, which provides the number of potential users that originate per unit of time in a certain location. More specifically, the origin-density model relates the rate of potential bike-sharing users that originate at a certain location with the residential population density, the presence of different points of interest (metro stations, cafes, hotels, stores, etc.) at the location, and more importantly, with the typical likelihood that users who originate at this location will find bicycles in nearby stations. The typical likelihood captures a user's expectation to find a bicycle, having the possibility to choose between different nearby stations and other options for commuting.

Published literature highlights the importance of the availability of bicycles as a key factor for ridership, which is even more important as the number of users and the size of the system increase. In this study, we determine the stations with the greatest demand to be able to adopt appropriate inventory policies in order to increase system availability.

With respect to the use of the Pareto law and ABC classification in inventory planning, Pareto is used as a grouping strategy, as well as an inventory planning tool [17], [18]. Relph et al. [19] mention that it is a simple and effective planning tool, but that the simultaneous use with the EOQ model can improve the selection of optimal inventory parameters. It is also the basis for some metaheuristic algorithms that are used to solve more complex inventory models, as shown in [20].

VII. METHODOLOGY

The methodology used in this research is the following:

A. Data Analysis and Problem Detection

The analysed data consists of the bicycle loan records, provided by BICIPUMA's management for the period comprised between October 2016 and December 2017. The database contains a total of 733,877 loan records, corresponding to loan periods of 2 to 20 minutes (required and allowed bicycle use time). The corresponding data analysis was carried out using R and provided the day and month of greatest demand, the highest and lowest demand station and average travel time.

The problem detection was carried out first through observation and direct use of the system (field work), to subsequently conduct a series of interviews with the various actors of the system including the Director of BICIPUMA, a module manager and the users. The BICIPUMA management indicated that there is no inventory control nor a demand forecast per service station, making the decision on how to cover the demand really difficult and causing several increments in the operational costs. Examples are a possible

surplus or lack of units in the service stations at different times, or greater possibilities of theft or damage to bicycles.

B. Proposed Solution

When observing the problems of the lack of bicycles, the loss of control of the units, the corresponding operational and inventory management issues a proposal arose.

Before elaborating an inventory forecast, it is necessary to carry out an analysis of the information that allows to recognize in a timely manner which are the service stations that, when implementing the proposed forecast, can help achieve a demand management and, therefore, a correct inventory control. The proposed data analysis corresponds to the Pareto Law in combination with an ABC classification.

C. Station Classification

The classification of the stations was carried out according to the following steps:

Step 1. Determination of the stations to be included.

To determine the busiest service stations, all 14 stations were included; the data provided by BICIPUMA was used for the corresponding analysis. The information was classified by station name and origin-destination frequencies.

Step 2. Building of the statistical table from the total sums of the observed frequencies.

Step 3. Construction and analysis of the corresponding Pareto diagram.

Step 4. ABC classification, considering 3 classes: class A, being the most crowded stations; class B, being the service stations of intermediate importance; and class C, being the least used stations.

VIII. RESULTS

The Pareto analysis of the BICIPUMA loan records for 2017 shows which 20% of the modules correspond to 80% of the total demand of the system. This analysis allows selecting the service stations with the highest demand level, in which it is convenient to carry out the characterization of the demand, perform goodness-of-fit tests, and subsequently develop and implement an appropriate inventory policy.

The results of the analysis are summarized in tables 1 and 2, which represent the total number of trips and corresponding relative and accumulated percentage for all service stations, considering respectively origin and destination. The most busy stations are ANEXO DE INGENIERIA, MEDICINA and BICICENTRO PA, although ANEXO DE INGENIERIA is the most arrival module (18% of all trips arrive to this station), while BICICENTRO PA is the most used departure module (16.6% of all trips). The high demand in these stations can be easily explained due to the location of the BICICENTRO PA and MEDICINA stations, respectively, near the *Universidad* subway station and the nearest access point to the *Copilco* subway station; both are also located near important roads. In

the case of the ANEXO DE INGENIERIA station, the arrival rates can be explained from its central and inner location, where there is no bus connection, as well as its proximity with 3 important student destinations, being the Accounting and Social Work Faculties, as well as an annex building of the Engineering Faculty.

TABLE 1: TRIP DISTRIBUTION FOR ORIGIN MODULES

Origin module	Nr of trips	Relative frequency (%)	Accumulated frequency (%)
BICICENTRO PA	121636	16.5	16.5
ANEXO DE INGENIERIA	101228	13.8	30.3
MEDICINA	87936	11.9	42.3
CIENCIAS	68233	9.3	51.6
INGENIERIA	53152	7.2	58.9
FILOSOFIA	52438	7.1	66.0
ESTADIO TAPATIO	43340	5.9	71.9
ARQUITECTURA	40896	5.6	77.5
DERECHO	39156	5.3	82.9
ESTADIO OLIMPICO	37663	5.1	87.9
QUIMICA	28465	3.9	91.8
CIENCIAS POLITICAS	22205	3.0	94.9
BICICENTRO PB	20207	2.7	97.6
PALOMAR	17322	2.4	100
TOTAL	733877		

TABLE 2: TRIP DISTRIBUTION FOR DESTINATION MODULES.

Destination module	Nr of trips	Relative frequency (%)	Accumulated frequency (%)
ANEXO DE INGENIERIA	132318	18.0	18.0
MEDICINA	114914	15.6	33.7
BICICENTRO PA	75491	10.3	43.9
CIENCIAS	68692	9.3	53.3
INGENIERIA	67546	9.2	62.5
FILOSOFIA	62481	8.5	71.0
DERECHO	46289	6.3	77.3
QUIMICA	35043	4.7	82.1
ESTADIO TAPATIO	32436	4.4	86.6
ARQUITECTURA	25918	3.5	90.1
BICICENTRO PB	22775	3.1	93.2

ESTADIO OLIMPICO	21427	2.9	96.1
CIENCIAS POLITICAS	18964	2.6	98.7
PALOMAR	9583	1.3	100.00
TOTAL	733877		

With the previous information, a Pareto diagram was elaborated and the accumulated distribution function was determined. Figures 3 and 4 represent respectively the Pareto chart for origin and destination modules.

Fig. 3. Pareto chart and distribution for origin modules

Fig. 4. Pareto chart and distribution for destination modules

Using the cumulative distribution presented in figures 3 and 4, an ABC analysis was conducted in which the classes were determined as follows:

ABC segmentation for the origin modules:

- **Class A** contains the departure modules that represent 82.9% of the exit demand
- **Class B** represents 12% of the exit demand
- **Class C** represents 5.1% of the exit demand.

ABC segmentation for the destination modules:

- **Class A** represents the destination modules with the highest number of entering bicycles, correspond to the 82.1% of turned-in bikes.
- **Class B** represents 11% of the destination modules.
- **Class C** represents the 6.9% less used destination modules.

Table 3 shows the modules' classification using the previously determined classes.

TABLE 3: ABC MODULES CLASSIFICATION

ORIGEN MODULE	ABC CLASS	DESTINATION MODULE	ABC CLASS
BICICENTRO PA	A	ANEXO DE INGENIERIA	A
ANEXO DE INGENIERIA	A	MEDICINA	A
MEDICINA	A	BICICENTRO PA	A
CIENCIAS	A	CIENCIAS	A
INGENIERIA	A	INGENIERIA	A

FILOSOFIA	A	FILOSOFIA	A
ESTADIO TAPATIO	A	DERECHO	A
ARQUITECTURA	A	QUIMICA	A
DERECHO	A	ESTADIO TAPATIO	B
ESTADIO OLIMPICO	B	ARQUITECTURA	B
QUIMICA	B	BICICENTRO PB	B
CIENCIAS POLITICAS	C	ESTADIO OLIMPICO	C
BICICENTRO PB	C	CIENCIAS POLITICAS	C
PALOMAR	C	PALOMAR	C

According to the obtained results, the modules to start the demand analysis with would be BICICENTRO PA, ANEXO DE INGENIERIA, MEDICINA, CIENCIAS and FILOSOFIA which are the modules with an A classification in both destination and origin modules. At a later stage, this can be replicated in the rest of the service stations, in order to obtain an appropriate inventory policy that reduces the replenishment cost.

IX. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a Pareto law and ABC analysis were presented as tools for analysing the demand of the BICIPUMA bike sharing system. The goal was to determine the starting point of the analysis; in this case, the stations whose optimal supply simultaneously minimizes the total cost of the system and maximize the service level.

During the development of this project, several problems were observed, such as the lack of precision in the inventory information in each of the stations; this hindered the corresponding data analysis and presents an opportunity for improvement in the future.

Due to the complexity of the system, given that the inventory must be complemented while the system is functioning and that the system corresponds to a dynamic network, the project was divided into phases. The first phase is the one presented in this article: a qualitative analysis that allows the recognition of the service modules with the greatest influx in the system and at first hand the mobility patterns in the university campus can be observed, so that it allows the management of the system to visualize how the students travel within faculty facilities. This analysis allows us to select the modules on which by the demand level it's advisable to carry out the characterization of the demand for the analysis of its behaviour, carrying out goodness-of-fit tests, and subsequently

developing and implementing an adequate inventory policy for each module.

The second phase consists of the development of an inventory forecast for these busy service stations, so that the transport of bicycles can be reduced, increasing their safeguard and care. On the other hand, the forecast makes it possible to predict the demand satisfactorily, without having a bicycle surplus in the service stations, which helps in avoiding damage and theft, among other situations. When the inventory forecast is developed, there are several issues that should be taken into consideration:

- **Its trend pattern:** due to the community's concern about the environment, the use of the system is expected to continue increasing,
- **Its cyclical pattern:** due to medium and long-term changes in the UNAM's policies,
- **Its seasonal pattern:** since the university works by semester, there are time ranges in which the bicycle use increases (at the beginning and in the middle of the semester) or decreases (during the holidays or at the end of the semester),
- **Unforeseen events:** due to the seismic vulnerability of Mexico City and the high degree of social and political awareness inherent to large universities, the possibility of events such as earthquakes or strikes must be considered.

Finally, the third phase involves the development of an inventory control system that allows BICIPUMA management to improve the performance of the system by having a just-in-time replenishment system and maximizing the control of the units and, therefore, minimizes the loss of bicycles and the waiting times of users.

At the end of these three phases, a simulation model can be used to compare the current system performance with that of an improved system, where the forecast and inventory control is adequately implemented. Through the data obtained for both scenarios, the real improvement can be quantified and the efficiency and effectiveness of the forecast and control can be measured.

In conclusion, the Pareto law and ABC analysis can be applied successfully in cases like this, where there is a lack of information; the corresponding results will help the system administration recognize where to start developing and implementing appropriate inventory and forecasting policies. These policies can be applied step by step or progressively, so that the administration can observe and control the changes and their implications, make the appropriate modifications to optimize the system and improve the quality of the provided loan service.

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